

Investigating the influence of hydrogen-rich fuel mixtures on the assessment of the flame transfer function

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Abstract

To achieve the decarbonization of electrical power generation, gas turbines need to be upgraded to combust high-hydrogen content fuels reliably. One of the main challenges in this upgrade is the burner design. A promising burner concept for a high-hydrogen fuel mixture is a jet burner, which is highly flashback resistant thanks to its high bulk velocity. Due to its non-acoustically compact extension and the presence of hydrogen in the fuel mixture, new challenges arise in assessing the (thermo)acoustic response of this burner design. A burner transfer matrix (BTM) and the flame transfer function (FTF) or transfer matrix (FTM) are typically measured with the multi-microphone method (MMM) to assess the performance of new burner types in relation to thermoacoustic stability. With the switch towards hydrogen, the fuel/air mixture is significantly altered in its properties regarding the speed of sound and density, which are of fundamental importance to acoustic propagation and the accuracy of the MMM. The influence of the modified gas composition on the reconstruction of BTMs and FTFs is investigated in this work by using an analytical model and experimental results. To do so, we adapt the preheating temperature during the measurement of the BTM with a non-reactive mixture to match the speed of sound of the hydrogen-air mixture required in reactive conditions. Additionally, we present an analytical model for the jet burner transfer matrix, which is validated against the experimental data showing good agreement. The influence of the variation in reactant composition of the BTM on the FTM assessment is noticeable. For the assessment of the FTF, the influence of the differing BTMs due to varying reactants is small on the phase values and noticeable in the gain values.

Keywords

Jet-Burner, Hydrogen, Flame Transfer Function, Thermoacoustics

Introduction

To limit the human impact on climate change, global electricity generation needs to be decarbonized. To achieve this target, a large share of energy must be produced from renewable sources. These sources are, however, intermittent. To guarantee a stable electrical grid, other on-demand power inputs are needed. This balancing power supply can be provided by stationary gas turbines. To future-proof stationary gas turbines, the use of carbon-free fuels is unavoidable. Therefore, burners for future gas turbines must be upgraded to be able to combust carbon-free fuels. Conventional gas turbine burner concepts such as swirl burners can reach a high level of hydrogen share of up to 60 vol.% (Noble et al. 2021). This seemingly large amount of hydrogen in the fuel composition is, however, insufficient to significantly reduce the CO₂ emission levels of gas turbines (Ciani et al. 2020). Higher hydrogen shares, greater than 70%, must be burned. A possible method to increase the hydrogen share limit is to use a high amount of steam to stabilize the swirl combustor (Göke and Paschereit 2013). A promising new solution is to use lean premixed jet burners for the combustion system, which are highly flashback resistant due to their high flow velocity (Lammel et al. 2017).

Lean premixed combustion suffers from the drawback of being susceptible to thermoacoustic instabilities (Lieuwen and Yang 2005; Poinso 2017). These instabilities may hinder the safe operation of the combustor and must be assessed in the early stages of a burner/combustor development. The flame transfer function (FTF) or flame transfer matrix (FTM) can be measured to assess the thermoacoustic properties of a newly developed combustor by means of the multi-microphone method (MMM) (Paschereit et al. 2002). This method relies on the knowledge of the burner acoustics, assessed by the burner transfer matrix (BTM). As a standard procedure, the BTM is measured at conditions where only (preheated) air is fed into the system. The acoustic properties of the burner, however, change when the gas fed to the burner is a mixture of (preheated) air and fuel. This is particularly true for hydrogen-rich fuels because the thermodynamic

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properties (density, heat capacities) of hydrogen vary significantly compared to those of pure air. These changes influence the actual acoustic response of a burner. The longer the burner, the larger the influence of the thermodynamic properties of the mixture on its response. This is particularly relevant for jet burners since they feature a relatively long tubular section required for flow-conditioning (see Figure 1).

The switch towards high-hydrogen content fuels poses new challenges in the assessment of the thermoacoustic response of a burner. First, the hydrogen composition influences the reconstruction of the acoustic field. Due to the strong difference in density and speed of sound of hydrogen compared to air, even small amounts of H_2 significantly change the properties of the composition. If not accounted for, this results in a significant reconstruction error of the MMM, also shown by (Blonde et al. 2023). Also, the speed of sound changes the propagation time through the burner, which is characterized to assess the FTM. Second, the jet burner design is challenging for the BTM and FTM reconstructions due to the longer extension of the burner compared to traditional swirl burners. This leads to a higher influence of the propagation time through the burner assessed by the BTM. Also, the Mach number in the burner's mixing tube is significantly higher than in conventional swirl burners, which influences the shape of the BTMs.

In this work, we will first investigate the methodology changes required to appropriately consider the high hydrogen content in the MMM reconstruction, followed by a study on the influence of hydrogen on the burner transfer matrix for perfectly and technically premixed conditions. We will conclude the work with a discussion on the influence of hydrogen content on the FTM and FTF.

Experimental setup

A generic piloted single hydrogen jet burner (POShyDON) is investigated in this study. The burner response is measured with two microphone arrays, one upstream and one downstream of the burner, each consisting of four microphones (G.R.A.S. 46 BP) that are non-uniformly spaced. The microphones are mounted into cooled holders to enable a safe operation for the hot conditions upstream and downstream of the burner element. The microphones are calibrated *a priori* with a pistonfon for absolute calibration and a calibration tube for relative phase calibration. Two sets of loudspeakers (B&C Speakers 18SW5-8) are mounted up- and downstream of the burner to provide (at least) two linearly independent forced acoustic fields needed for the multi-microphone method. The upstream set consists of four loudspeakers, whereas the downstream consists of two loudspeakers. We refer to Fig. 1 for a detailed description of the test rig.

With reference to the bottom inset of Fig. 1, the POSHyDON burner can be divided into four main components: an inlet nozzle (starting from A), a fuel injector (right before B), a mixing tube (extending from B to C), and a dump plate. The tube length is chosen to be approximately ten times the diameter D of the pipe. This is done to align the flow and enhance the mixing of the reactants for the combustion (flow conditioning). In this study, two fuel injectors are tested. The first is the fuel injection line entering

Figure 1. Top: Schematic of the entire experimental test rig, comprising a combustion chamber enclosed between two duct sections allowing for the reconstruction of the acoustic fields with the MMM. Bottom: Detailed view of the POSHyDON burner. Capital letters indicate reference planes for area changes, and the numbers indicate propagation zones.

the jet burner, depicted in the bottom inset of Fig. 1. The second is a fuel injection situated further upstream of the upstream loudspeakers, indicated in the top inset of Fig. 1, guaranteeing a better level of spatial mixing of reactant. A downstream anechoic termination is designed for each condition as in Bechert (1980) to avoid the occurrence of thermoacoustic instabilities during the MMM measurements.

Methodology

The flame transfer matrix is measured to assess the flame response to the acoustics. It is typically measured with the multi-microphone method, which relates the pressure signals of two or more microphones to the propagation of planar acoustic waves (Jang and Ih 1998; Alemela et al. 2008). To detect the downstream and upstream traveling planar acoustic waves, \hat{f} and \hat{g} respectively, the following relation is used

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{p}_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-i\omega \frac{x_1}{\bar{c} + \bar{u}}} & e^{i\omega \frac{x_1}{\bar{c} - \bar{u}}} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ e^{-i\omega \frac{x_N}{\bar{c} + \bar{u}}} & e^{i\omega \frac{x_N}{\bar{c} - \bar{u}}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{f} \\ \hat{g} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

with N the number of microphone signals available, \bar{c} the speed of sound, \bar{u} the velocity in the microphone section, and ω the angular frequency. When $N > 2$, the system of equations (1) is over-defined and can be solved in a least squares sense. To determine the transfer matrix,

two independent acoustic fields are required. They are provided by activating once only the upstream-mounted loudspeakers and once only the downstream ones, resulting in the following scattering matrix (SM)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{f}_d \\ \hat{g}_u \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} T_{du} & R_{dd} \\ R_{uu} & T_{ud} \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{SM}} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{f}_u \\ \hat{g}_d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

with u and d denoting the duct sections upstream and downstream the burner, respectively. The diagonal elements T are the transmission coefficients of the planar waves through the burner, and R are the reflections on each side of the burner. The SM can be converted into a transfer matrix (TM), which relates the primitive variables of velocity and pressure fluctuations instead of relating the opposite-directed traveling waves.

In practice, it is impossible to measure the flame transfer matrix directly due to the pressure transducers always capturing the acoustic properties of the burner together with the flame. Therefore, the experiment captures the flame-burner transfer matrix (FBTM) once the flame is ignited. To acquire the FTM, the BTM has to be determined and its contribution removed from the FBTM:

$$\text{FTM} = \text{FBTM} \cdot \text{BTM}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

For the BTM and FBTM measurements, the reference plane is selected as the burner inlet plane (A) for the upstream forcing measurement and as the burner exit plane (C) for the downstream forcing measurement. During the FBTM measurements, the acoustic forcing is regulated to have a constant amplitude (5% of the mean flow) at the burner outlet plane on the cold side, by assessing the velocity fluctuations with the upstream microphone array for both forcing conditions. The BTM measured with the non-reactive mixture evaluates the velocity fluctuations at the burner exit.

Analytical model of the burner transfer matrix

For the following investigation, an analytical model for the acoustic response of the POSHyDON burner is constructed to assess how the key parameters influence the BTM. The model relates the acoustic fluctuations upstream and downstream of the jet burner via the burner transfer matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{p} \\ \hat{u} \end{bmatrix}_d = \text{BTM} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p} \\ \hat{u} \end{bmatrix}_u, \quad (4)$$

with $\hat{p}/(\bar{\rho}\bar{c}) = \tilde{p}$ denoting the normalised primitive variable. The BTM is composed of a chain of plane wave-propagation zones and area changes (see Fig. 1).

The propagation element of a straight duct with a constant cross-section area and a uniform mean flow is expressed by:

$$\text{TM}_j = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} e^{i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1-M)}} + e^{-i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1+M)}} & -e^{i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1-M)}} + e^{-i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1+M)}} \\ -e^{i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1-M)}} + e^{-i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1+M)}} & e^{i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1-M)}} + e^{-i\frac{\omega L}{\bar{c}(1+M)}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where L denotes the length of the element and M the Mach number $M \equiv \bar{u}/\bar{c}$. The index j denotes the section in which the propagation model is used. The parameters for this model are known from the burner geometry, the mass flow, and the

chemical composition of the air/fuel blend. This model is used to propagate the acoustic wave in sections 1, 2, and 3 of Fig. 1.

For the area change (contraction and expansion), the following model is used as in Polifke (2004):

$$\mathbf{J}_x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \zeta_x M_x - ikL_{\text{eff},x} \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

with M_x denoting the upstream Mach number, the subscript x the reference plane (A,B or C in Fig. 1), $\alpha = A_{us}/A_{ds}$ the ratio of cross-section areas, and ζ_x the loss coefficient. $L_{\text{eff},x}$ is the effective length of the area change and is estimated as described by Gentemann et al. (2003). The values for ζ are obtained by fitting them to the experimental values acquired. A simulated annealing algorithm, chosen due to its global optimization ability, performs this computation. The optimizer identifies the loss coefficients by minimizing the value of the L1 norm between the model and the experimental results for all experiments.

By concatenating wave propagation elements and area change elements, the model for the POSHyDON burner is derived as follows:

$$\text{BTM} = \mathbf{J}_C \text{TM}_3 \mathbf{J}_B \text{TM}_2 \mathbf{J}_A \text{TM}_1. \quad (7)$$

The presence of H_2 in the reactive mixture changes the BTM, because it alters the value of the speed of sound and mean flow that enter in the propagation and area jump matrices. This results in changes in the evaluation of the acoustic forcing velocities u'/\bar{u} , which in turn, changes the reconstruction of the FTF.

Assessing the FTF from the FTM

From a theoretical perspective, the Rankine-Hugoniot equations can be used to describe the jump conditions across an acoustically compact heat element, yielding an explicit expression for the FTM (Alemela et al. (2008)):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_d \\ \hat{u}_d \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \beta & -\beta(T_r - 1)M_1(1 + \text{FTF}) \\ -(T_r - 1)\gamma M_1 & 1 + (T_r - 1)\text{FTF} \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{FTM}} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_u \\ \hat{u}_u \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

$T_r = T_d/T_u$ denotes the temperature ratio across the flame. This relation assumes low Mach numbers and a stiff fuel injection, resulting in no pressure fluctuation in the fuel supply. In this study, T_d is estimated to be 90% of the adiabatic flame temperature to account for heat loss due to the cooling and the radiation through the quartz combustion chamber. The ratio of specific impedances is defined by $\beta \equiv (\bar{\rho}_u \bar{c}_u)/(\bar{\rho}_d \bar{c}_d)$, and γ is the ratio of specific heats. The FTF is defined as

$$\text{FTF}(\omega) = \frac{q'(\omega)/\bar{q}(\omega)}{u'(\omega)/\bar{u}(\omega)}. \quad (9)$$

The FTF relates the heat release rate fluctuations to the velocity fluctuations of the flame and can be extracted from the FTM. If the Mach number of the flame element is low, $M \ll 1$, then $\hat{p}_{us} \approx \hat{p}_{ds}$ and, Eq. (10) simplifies into (Bobusch et al. 2012)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}_d \\ \hat{u}_d \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 1 + (T_r - 1)\text{FTF} \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{FTM}} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_u \\ \hat{u}_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The FTF can be evaluated by

$$\text{FTF} = \frac{\text{FTM}_{22} - 1}{T_r - 1}, \quad (11)$$

with FTM_{22} denoting the bottom right element of the FTM.

Results

We now discuss the influence of changes in the mixture on the BTM and, consequently, on the measured FTM. First, the influence of the parameters in the multi-microphone reconstruction is investigated. Second, the influence of the difference in speed of sound and density on the BTM is discussed. We use the previously introduced model and compare it to measured data, considering variations in the properties of the mixture propagating through the burner. Third, we investigate the influence of the BTM on the FTM by evaluating the same flame conditions twice with differing BTMs. For these investigations, we will show three different conditions. The conditions represent the mixture required for the burner to operate at a thermal power of 100 kW with an air mass flow of 220 kg/h. This is done for natural gas (NG), hydrogen (H_2), and a reference condition without fuel further denoted as ‘‘Air’’. The resulting thermodynamic and combustion parameters for each of the mixtures considered are displayed in Tab. 1. For methane, the density and speed of sound variations in comparison to the pure air case are minimal, which explains why these effects were never considered in detail in the past. However, for the hydrogen-air mixture, the density and the speed of sound significantly differ from the condition with pure air. They may induce significant errors in the BTM and FTM reconstructions. For a precise assessment of the BTM, the change in the speed of sound of the reactive mixture needs to be accounted for. It is, however, not possible to measure a BTM while injecting a reactive fuel composition without combusting it due to safety and environmental concerns. To evaluate experimentally a BTM with the properties of the fuel/air mixture, therefore, we adapt the speed of sound of pure Air by increasing the preheating temperature T_{in} . These values and the corresponding speed of sound and density are denoted with a subscript c in Table 1. The preheating temperature is increased to match the speed of sound c . This procedure does not generally guarantee that the density of the heated air matches the one of the fuel/air mixture. For the condition investigated in this configuration, this difference is, however, only 1%.

Fuel	\dot{m}_{fuel} [kg/h]	$\bar{\rho}$ [kg/m ³]	\bar{c} [m/s]	T_{in} [°C]	T_{ad} [°C]	ϕ
Air	-	0.6159	476.27	300	-	-
Air + NG	7.5	0.6000	479.09	300	1537	0.563
Air + H_2	3	0.5221	517.87	300	1528	0.466
Air _{c,NG}	-	0.6084	479.09	307	-	-
Air _{c,H₂}	-	0.5227	517.87	410	-	-

Table 1. Density and sound speed values for varying fuel types for a flame with constant thermal power $P_{\text{th}} = 100$ kW and an air mass flow of 220 kg/h. In the first row, the reference values are displayed for the conditions with pure air. For all cases, a preheating temperature of 300°C is chosen. The values with the subscript $-c$ are corrected to match the speed of the fuel/air mixture with pure air by changing the preheating temperature T_{in} . While the density and speed of sound of Air+NG mixtures are similar to those of pure Air, they are significantly altered for Air+ H_2 mixtures.

Figure 2. Influence of the gas properties on the speed of sound and density for the reaction educts and products. A comparison between the influence of hydrogen and methane. The values are normed to the reference conditions with air. The preheating temperature of $T_{\text{in}} = 300^\circ\text{C}$ is assumed as the input temperature. For the combustion products, the adiabatic flame temperature is used. The shaded areas denote the influence of a variation of $\pm 5\%$ of the corresponding temperature on the speed of sound and density. For simplicity reasons, the natural gas is assumed to be methane.

Influence of the fuel on the multi-microphone method reconstruction

For the reconstruction of the acoustic waves from the multi-microphone method, Eq. (1) is used. The solutions are derived by a least-square method. In this section, we will discuss the influence of changing the gas properties on this method. From Eq. (1), it is evident that changes in the speed of sound \bar{c} and mean flow velocity \bar{u} affect the acoustic waves reconstruction. The gas properties of the fuel/air mixture vary both the speed of sound \bar{c} and the velocity \bar{u} . The latter

Figure 3. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the BTM measured with the MMM. The values are displayed for the three reference cases as stated in Tab. 1, and additionally, the equivalence ratio of the hydrogen condition is varied in steps of $\phi = 0.1$.

is due to the fact that experimentally, the mass flow rate \dot{m} is kept constant by a Coriolis mass flow control, independent of the density ρ , and the mean flow velocity, therefore, depends on the density, according to the relation

$$\bar{u} = \frac{\dot{m}}{A\rho}, \quad (12)$$

where A denotes the cross-section area, which is fixed by the geometry. Referring again to Eq. (1), we also note that errors in the speed of sound and density are scaled by the distance of the microphones to the reference plane x_N ; the larger the distance, the higher the reconstruction error. In our setup, the largest distances between the reference planes and the furthest microphones are approximately 0.5 m upstream and 1 meter downstream.

To investigate the effect of changing fuel compositions on the speed of sound and density we vary the equivalence ratio ϕ of the mixture composition, and we plot the relative errors of the gas properties compared to those of air. Fig. 2 displays the variation in density, speed of sound, and $\bar{c} + \bar{u}$ normalized to a reference condition. This reference condition is chosen differently for the educts and products of the combustion process. For the educts, preheated air is used

as a reference; for the products, the air temperature is assumed to match the adiabatic flame temperature. In the case of a BTM measurement, both microphone segments see the gas properties of educts since no combustion is taking place. For the FBTM measurement, the upstream microphone section sees the educt gas properties, and the downstream section sees the product gas properties, which are obtained using Cantera (Goodwin et al. 2022). For the speed of sound plotted in Fig. 2, the gas properties of methane over ϕ only slightly change for the educts and products, with a maximal error below 2%. On the other hand, the gas properties change significantly for the hydrogen mixtures as the hydrogen content is increased. The variation is higher for the educts than for the products due to the different chemical composition of the combustion products. Focusing on the variation of the gas properties in the products, one can see that the deviation of the speed of sound is significantly higher for hydrogen. This is due to the fact that water vapor, the main product of H₂ combustion, has a speed of sound much higher than carbon dioxide, present only in NG combustion. The variation of the gas properties in the educts for the hydrogen combustion is larger

Figure 4. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the modeled and experimentally measured BTM. The mass flow rate is adapted accordingly to the fuel mass flow rate.

the larger the equivalence ratio, and reaches values up to 19% for the speed of sound. Similar trends are observed for the density of the mixtures, with hydrogen reducing the density significantly, with a deviation of the educts of up to 29%. The error in the reconstruction of the acoustic field is characterized by the quantity $\bar{c} \pm \bar{u}$ from Eq. (1). Also here, the deviation is larger for H₂ combustion, implying that the MMM will suffer of larger errors if the gas properties are not appropriately considered, which will propagate in the BTM. To demonstrate this, in Fig. 3, we display the influence that varying the gas properties has on the reconstruction of the BTM. To do this, the properties of the gas are artificially set to those of NG/H₂ in the MMM reconstruction. This effect is shown only for the BTM and not the FTM, since the BTM is measured with the educt properties in both microphone sections, resulting in a higher error. Also, the BTM is directly measured, whereas the FTM is not and the error propagation less trivial. Nevertheless, this error source has to be also accounted for in the FBTM measurement.

Figure 3 shows that the BTMs reconstructed when using Air of CH₄ properties closely match for the absolute and phase values. This is due to the small variation in gas properties of the methane/air mixture. Instead, for the hydrogen mixture, this is not the case. For the reference condition shown in Tab. 1, the values for the absolute

elements of $|BTM_{11}|, |BTM_{21}|, |BTM_{22}|$ are at least doubled in the frequency range of 200 - 400 Hz. This effect increases with increasing equivalence ratio due to the higher hydrogen share in the mixture. For the $|BTM_{12}|$ element, this influence is not as clearly visible due to the comparably higher values of this element. The phase values, shown in Fig. 3b, do not display a strong influence on the gas properties for this burner geometry. The reconstruction error lies mainly in the wrong assessment of the absolute values and affects the phase values less.

We have shown how, even though the amount of fuel is lower than 1.5% (in mass) for the reference conditions, the presence of hydrogen in the composition significantly influences the MMM reconstruction and, in turn, the shape of the BTM and, therefore, the FTM. One should, therefore always use the correct speed of sound and density for each fuel/air mixture.

Influence of fuel variation on the assessment of the BTM

In this section, the burner acoustics are characterized. The derived model in the previous section depends on the Mach number. The Mach number itself depends on the density and the speed of sound – thus, the fuel composition. The

comparison between the BTM obtained experimentally and the model is displayed in Fig. 4. Because all experiments are performed with air, the preheating air temperature of the experiment was adjusted to adjust the speed of sound of the experiment to that of the model with fuel. The parameters for the model are taken from the assumed mixture for the combustion (see Tab. 1). The good comparison between the theoretical and experimental results confirms that the calculation of a BTM by changing the preheating temperature is a viable solution to account for the variation in the speed of sound of fuel/air compositions. Additionally, the derived model allows us to compute a BTM for the technically premixed conditions, therefore altering the gas properties only within the mixing tube, and not in the MMM section, which cannot be achieved experimentally. For the technical premixed modeling, it is assumed that the fuel is injected right before the area change at section B (see Fig. 1). The BTM gain and phase of the model for the technically premixed conditions are also shown in Fig. 4.

All elements of the BTM obtained from the theoretical model match the experimental values, with some minor differences. Notably, in the low-frequency limit below 150 Hz, the values of the experimentally measured conditions differ; this may be due to the reconstruction error induced by the finite length of the microphone tube, which, compared to the long wavelength at low frequency, is short (Alemela et al. 2008). This increases the error in the reconstruction since the microphones discretize only a small part of the acoustic wave. For the absolute values, the $|\text{BTM}_{11}|$ at a frequency above 550 Hz deviates from the model's absolute values. This deviation is due to higher reconstruction errors caused by uncertainties in the calibration factors of the used microphones. The $|\text{BTM}_{12}|$ element of the model is in good agreement with the measured ones, resulting in relatively high values compared to the other BTM elements. This element relates the downstream pressure fluctuations \tilde{p}_d to the upstream velocity fluctuations \hat{u}_u . Therefore, the upstream velocity fluctuation has a high gain on the downstream pressure fluctuations. The $|\text{BTM}_{21}|$ element, which relates the downstream velocity fluctuations to the upstream pressure fluctuations, is low compared to the other elements, indicating that the influence of the upstream pressure fluctuations on the downstream velocity fluctuations is dampened through the burner. The $|\text{BTM}_{22}|$ element, which relates upstream to downstream velocity fluctuations, has an approximate constant value of about 2, corresponding to the ratio between the downstream and upstream cross-section areas, $\alpha = 2.01$ in Eq. (6). The phase values shown in Fig. 4b demonstrate a good agreement between the experimental and analytical results. An exception are the $\angle\text{BTM}_{11}$ values in the low-frequency limit, which may again be due to the long wavelength compared to the microphone spacing, resulting in a worse discretization of the acoustic wave.

A technically premixed investigation is performed only on hydrogen since the results of the natural the gas composition already do not display significant differences. Figure 4 shows the BTM results for the technically premixed conditions with H_2 . The BTM model results are comparable to those of the perfectly premixed hydrogen case. This is probably due to the length of the mixing tube, which is 10 times the tube

Figure 5. Influence of the fuel composition on the BTM. The relative error between the adapted conditions and the conventionally measured BTM with air is shown. The detailed values for the reference conditions are displayed in Tab. 1

diameter. The change in speed of sound and, therefore, the propagation time of the mixture has to be accounted for in the BTM. There still is a small error in assuming that the BTM of the technically equals the premixed one, but this should be comparatively small and, therefore, could be neglected.

To better highlight the differences between the three operating conditions for the measurement of the BTM, we display in Fig. 5 the difference between the BTMs with air/fuel mixture and those measured with air. The difference is computed in the complex space, and the relative error is taken.

It can be seen that, in the $|\text{BTM}_{\text{rel},11}|$ and the $|\text{BTM}_{\text{rel},12}|$ elements, the relative error has comparable results for the experimental and modeled values, confirming that the variation of the BTM is due to the variation in speed of sound. The relative error is prominent at higher frequencies, peaking at 620 Hz with values for both elements above 150% for the hydrogen conditions. Still, even for lower frequencies, the difference ranges up to 50% in the hydrogen cases. Again, the modeled values of the BTM for natural gas conditions do not strongly influence the BTM, which is expected since the variation of the speed of sound and density with natural gas is minimal. For the $|\text{BTM}_{\text{rel},21}|$ and the $|\text{BTM}_{\text{rel},22}|$ element, the experimental results do

Figure 6. Absolute values of the single elements of the FTM for hydrogen combustion (see. Table 1) with the perfectly premixed injector. The color corresponds to the previously displayed BTM.

not as closely match the modeled ones. This is due to the values of the BTM approximating zero for the $|BTM_{rel,21}|$ element. Therefore, the measurement precision error of the experiments is higher for these elements. For the $|BTM_{rel,22}|$ element, the error is fluctuating; this could be due to the fluctuations seen in the experimental values in Fig. 4a, which are not fully captured by the model.

Overall, hydrogen’s influence on the BTM is significant for reconstructing the downstream pressure fluctuations and should not be neglected if the BTMs are compared. Also, on the $|BTM_{22}|$ element, a clear influence of the varying BTMs can be observed. This is especially the case for the burner investigated in this study; due to its significant length, the propagation time through the burner is altered with differing sound speeds (see Eq. (5)). In the following, we will investigate the influence of the BTM on the FTM and FTF.

Influence of an error in the BTM on the FTM

The influence of the fuel/air compositions on the BTMs transfers nontrivially into the assessment of the FTMs. The influence of errors in the BTM on the FTM will be shown here. The FTM of the natural gas conditions will not be shown since the variation of the BTM is small. For the hydrogen cases, two FTMs were measured: one with the conventionally measured BTM with air and an FTM with the

corrected BTM to hydrogen gas properties. The results are shown in Fig. 6.

The FBTM has to be measured twice and can not be assessed by changing the BTM in the post-processing. This is because the BTM is used to assess the forcing amplitude on the cold side of the flame for the measurement of the FBTM and is kept constant at 5%. If the BTM is changed in the post-processing, this could lead to differing assumed forcing amplitudes upstream of the flame. A too-low forcing would result in a noisy measurement, whereas a too-high forcing may alter the results due to the presence of nonlinearities in the flame response.

In the low-frequency limit, the absolute values of the FTM reach high values. This may be due to a coupling of the acoustic excitation with the fuel line, resulting in the (spatially) perfectly premixed injection not being temporally premixed. An expression of the FTM can be derived as in Eq. 10, considering the low Mach number assumption is fulfilled and the injection is stiff. If these criteria are fulfilled, the $|FTM_{11}|$ element should be approximately $\beta = 1.55$, which is the case for frequencies above 200 Hz. In the low-frequency limit, the injection can not be assumed to be stiff, resulting in deviating values. The $|FTM_{21}|$ element should be approximately zero, which can again be assumed for values above 200 Hz. The $|FTM_{12}|$ element should again be approximately zero, the measured results indicate higher values of up to ten for frequencies above 200 Hz. Nonetheless, by comparing the values of

the $|\text{FTM}_{12}|$ element to the derived values from $-\beta(T_r - 1)M_1(1 + \text{FTF})$, we found that the magnitude of the values is comparable, indicating that the values can be assumed to be small and the low Mach number assumption is not violated.

The FTM results for the absolute values overall show in a comparable trend. The $|\text{FTM}_{11}|$ and $|\text{FTM}_{21}|$ elements show an increase in the absolute values if the gas properties are accounted for in the BTM measurement. The $|\text{FTM}_{11}|$ and $|\text{FTM}_{22}|$ elements instead show the opposite trend. The phase results of the FTMs do show a significantly smaller difference induced by the change in BTM. This smaller influence of the BTM is expected since it was shown that the variation in gas composition mainly affects the absolute values of the BTM. To properly assess the FTM, the influence of the gas compositions needs to be accounted for in the BTM. If this is not accounted for, the absolute values show differing absolute values.

Extracting an FTF from the FTM

An FTF can be extracted from the FTM by Eq. (11). The results for the perfectly premixed conditions are displayed in Fig. 7. The NG condition was measured only once since the influence of the variation in gas composition is assumed to be small.

Figure 7. FTF values derived from the FTM for the perfectly premixed conditions. The color denotes the used BTM for the evaluation of the FTM. The operational conditions are noted in Tab. 1.

The comparison between the two measurements with differing BTM for the hydrogen conditions demonstrates a clear influence of the correction of the gas properties of the BTMs by nearly halving the gain values of the FTF. Demonstrating that if not accounted for, the values of the FTF for high hydrogen shares are overestimated. The phase values of the two FTFs for the hydrogen conditions display a comparable trend with a shift at approximately 290 Hz. A similar phase shift can be found in the measurements of $|\text{BTM}_{11}|$ element. The influence of the correction of the

BTM on the phase is comparably small to the influence of the gain.

The FTFs show the previously noted coupling of the fuel supply with the forcing, resulting in a high low-frequency limit for the absolute values. Instead, the phase values converge towards zero for the hydrogen and natural gas conditions. The slope of the phase is interestingly extremely flat, with a jump of the phase of π at 270 Hz for NG and 300 Hz for hydrogen, which can be related to the minimum gain values of the FTF at the same frequency. The FTF gain displays two peaks in the gain for the natural gas conditions, a first at approximately 180 Hz and a second at 330 Hz. These peaks could be an interaction of multiple effects, for example, the hydrodynamic interaction and the coupling of the injection. For the hydrogen condition, only one peak is observed at the higher frequency of 400 Hz. By assessing a time delay from the phase values from the slope between the first and last measured value, for hydrogen (with the corrected BTM) and NG, a resulting $\tau_{1,H_2} = 4.1$ ms and $\tau_{1,NG} = 3.0$ ms, with a characteristic frequency of $f_{\text{cutoff},NG} = 239$ Hz and $f_{\text{cutoff},H_2} = 335$ Hz respectively. We note that these frequencies correspond to the minima in the absolute values and the phase jump of π for both operating conditions.

Additionally, we measured for the same reference conditions FTMs for a technically premixed injection without accounting for the influence of the BTM. The investigation of the FTM for the technically premixed injection showed a clear influence on the modeled BTM for hydrogen conditions. Therefore, the absolute values of the hydrogen condition can not be properly quantified. Changing the BTM afterward is not feasible due to a misjudgment in the forcing amplitude, leading to the nonphysical behavior of the FTM. We show the measured FTFs in the Appendix.

Conclusion

In this study, we discussed potential error sources when measuring the acoustic response of hydrogen flames instead of methane ones. First, we investigated the influence that the gas composition has on the speed of sound and, consequently, on the acoustic wave reconstruction with the MMM. This error is significantly higher for the hydrogen case due to a significant change in the speed of sound of the mixture. Our results show that it is crucial to account for the appropriate properties of the reactive mixture in the microphone section to reconstruct the planar waves properly. Second, we discuss the influence of the composition on the BTM, which is used to obtain an FTM. The BTM must be measured with air (or alternatively, with an inert gas like helium), which has thermodynamic properties similar to methane but very different from H_2 . To assess the influence of the H_2 mixture's properties on the measurements, we proposed to measure a BTM at an elevated temperature to correct for the influence of the speed of sound induced by the high hydrogen share. We investigated this influence with an analytical model of the presented burner. The results of the analytical model and the experiments are in good agreement. We found that the error for the methane-air mixture can be assumed to be small. Still, the errors for the hydrogen-air conditions result in slightly differing values of the BTM,

especially for the $|BTM_{11}|$ and $|BTM_{12}|$ elements at high frequency. We found that even if the BTM slightly varies for the hydrogen conditions investigated, the influence on the FTM is noticeable in the absolute results and minor in the phase results. For the assessment of the FTF, the influence of not accounting for the change in gas properties for high hydrogen shares leads to an overestimation of the absolute values of the FTF on the whole frequency range. The influence on the phase values is minor compared to the absolute values. Accounting for the correct gas properties in the BTM assessment is crucial for assessing the FTM and FTF of a jet burner operated with high hydrogen shares.

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Appendix

Additionally, we measured two FTFs with the air BTM for technically premixed conditions, as shown in Fig 8. For these FTFs, the air BTM was used; unfortunately, a *a posteriori* change of the BTM can not be performed since it would result in unprecise forcing amplitudes.

The values of technically premixed conditions of the gain and phase from the FTF converge towards zero both for the absolute and the phase values, which is expected as described in Polifke (2011). Also, these BTMs show a flattened phase curve for higher frequencies.

plot ppt

Figure 8. FTF values derived from the FTM for the technically and perfectly premixed conditions. The color denotes the used BTM for the evaluation of the FTM. The operational conditions are noted in Tab. 1.

Figure 9. FTF values derived from the FTM for the technically and perfectly premixed conditions. The color denotes the used BTM for the evaluation of the FTM. The operational conditions are noted in Tab. 1.

(a) Absolute Values

(b) Phase Values

Figure 10. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the BTM measured with the MMM. The values are displayed for the three reference cases as stated in Tab. 1, and additionally, the equivalence ratio of the hydrogen condition is varied in steps of $\phi = 0.1$.

Figure 11. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the modeled and experimentally measured BTM. The mass flow rate is adapted accordingly to the fuel mass flow rate.

(a) Absolute Values

(b) Phase Values

Figure 12. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the modeled and experimentally measured BTM. The mass flow rate is adapted accordingly to the fuel mass flow rate.

(a) Absolute Values

(b) Phase Values

Figure 13. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the modeled and experimentally measured BTM. The mass flow rate is adapted accordingly to the fuel mass flow rate.

(a) Absolute Values

(b) Phase Values

Figure 14. Influence of the fuel composition on the values of the modeled and experimentally measured BTM. The mass flow rate is adapted accordingly to the fuel mass flow rate.

Figure 15. Influence of the fuel composition on the BTM. The relative error between the adapted conditions and the conventionally measured BTM with air is shown. The detailed values for the reference conditions are displayed in Tab. 1

Figure 16. Absolute values of the single elements of the FTM for hydrogen combustion (see. Table 1) with the perfectly premixed injector. The color corresponds to the previously displayed BTM.